

Dye-sensitized photochemical transformation of some pharmaceutical drugs by singlet molecular oxygen

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Manuscript received 22 May 2008, accepted 12 January 2009

Abstract : Dye-sensitized photo-oxygenation of thiopentone and phenytoin by singlet molecular oxygen has been carried out under various reaction conditions, including variation of solvents and sensitizers. The product has been isolated and characterized by elemental analysis, physical, chemical and spectral data. A suitable mechanism has been proposed for the formation of photo product. To confirm the participation of singlet oxygen in the reaction, singlet oxygen scavengers have been used in the photo-oxygenation reaction.

Keywords : Photo-oxidation, singlet molecular oxygen, thiopentone, phenytoin, dye sensitizer.

Introduction

Pharmaceutical drugs with sensitive sites are susceptible to oxidation by singlet molecular oxygen and the oxidized product may or may not have the same biological activity than that of the parent pharmaceutical drug. In some cases, the product may be more effective or may lose efficacy completely. This kind of study will open newer avenues related to comparative biological activities of original pharmaceutical drug and its oxidized products.

The most general molecular orbital configuration for oxygen which arise from LCAO-MO configuration is $\delta_{2s}^2 \cdot \sigma_{2s}^{*2} \cdot \sigma_{2p_z}^2 \cdot (\pi_{2p_x})^2 (\pi_{2p_y})^2 \cdot (\pi_{2p_x}^*)^1 \cdot (\pi_{2p_y}^*)^1$. The lowest energy configuration is a triplet ground state to achieve minimum electron repulsion (Hund's rule). The last two valence electron enters one each into the degenerated π^*2p_x and π^*2p_y pair of orbitals with parallel spins giving triplet ground state $^3\Sigma_g^-$ which is represented as :

The two electronically excited states are $^1\Delta_g$ and $^1\Sigma_g^+$ states which arise from the same electronic configuration i.e. these do not involve promotion of an electron to higher orbitals. The pairing of two electrons in one molecular orbital results in the $^1\Delta_g$ state. This is a doubly degene-

rated state ($^1\Delta_g^+$ and $^1\Delta_g^-$). The spin pairing in different orbitals results in $^1\Sigma_g^+$ state. These states can be represented as :

Singlet oxygen has been found to be an active oxidizing species for a number of biological compounds¹⁻⁶. The toxicity of paraquat(1,1'-dimethyl-4,4'-bipyridilium dichloride), a broad spectrum herbicide was studied by Bus *et al.*⁷. Yasui *et al.*⁸ proposed singlet molecular oxygen involvement in rat and human cytochrome P450 dependent substrate oxidation. Arnold *et al.*⁹ studied photochemical fate of pharmaceutical compounds like cimetidine and ranitidine hydrochloride susceptible to attack by singlet molecular oxygen. Similarly, Packer *et al.*¹⁰ studied the effect of singlet oxygen on naproxen, dichlofenac, chlofibric acid and ibuprofen. Antioxidant properties of therapeutic drugs and photo-oxidation of the ophthalmic

drugs was studied by Garcia *et al.*¹¹⁻¹³. Capparelli *et al.*¹⁴ carried out photooxidation of pterin in aqueous solution. Formation of spiroiminodihydantoin nucleoside from 2'-deoxyguanosine oxidation by [(18)O-labeled] singlet molecular oxygen in aqueous solution was carried out by Martinez *et al.*¹⁵. Lima *et al.*¹⁶ studied new non-cellular fluorescence microplate screening assay for scavenging activity against singlet oxygen. Singlet molecular oxygen [O(2)((1)Delta (g))]-mediated photodegradation of tyrosine derivatives in the presence of cationic and neutral micellar systems have also been reported by Criado *et al.*¹⁷.

The present work has been undertaken to investigate the photooxidation of thiopentone which is a rapid-onset short acting barbiturate general anesthetic drug and phenytoin which is an anti-epileptic drug use to control seizures by singlet molecular oxygen.

Experimental

Thiopentone

Phenytoin

0.5 g of the drug was dissolved in 50 mL doubly distilled water. A few drops of the methylene blue was added to this solution such that concentration of methylene blue in the reaction mixture was $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. The solution was then irradiated with a light source. A water filter was used to avoid infrared radiations. The air was continuously bubbled in the reaction mixture by an aerator.

The progress of reaction was observed with the help of thin layer chromatography (TLC) at regular time intervals. Solvent system employed for TLC was chloroform : acetone (19 : 1) and chloroform : methanol (99 : 1) for thiopentone and phenytoin, respectively. In case of thiopentone, after 10 h of irradiation TLC plate shows two spots, one ($R_f = 0.33$) corresponding to the substrate (thiopentone) and another ($R_f = 0.18$) corresponding to the product while in case of phenytoin, after 46 h of irradiation TLC plate showed two spots, one ($R_f = 0.26$) corresponding to substrate (phenytoin) and another ($R_f = 0.31$) corresponding to the product. The reaction was then allowed to complete.

The irradiation was stopped when TLC plate showed

one spot corresponding to the product. The solution was then decolorized with the activated animal charcoal and the decolorized solution was allowed to evaporate. A solid of golden and brown crystals was obtained in thiopentone mixture and phenytoin mixture, respectively.

Effect of the triplet energy of sensitizer :

Triplet energies of sensitizer played a key role in photooxidation process. Photooxidation of thiopentone and phenytoin have been carried out in presence of different sensitizer by keeping all factors identical. The effect of sensitizers on the yield of photoproduct is reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of the triplet energy of sensitizer

[Sensitizer] = $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, irradiation time = 13 h, irradiation time = 49 h

Sensitizer	Triplet energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Yield (%)	
		Thiopentone	Phenytoin
Methylene blue	34.0	21.9	10.2
Rose Bengal	34.5-42.2	21.1	9.9
Eosin	43.2-46.0	20.9	9.3
Fluorescein	45.2-48.1	20.3	9.5

It was observed that as the triplet energy of the sensitizer was increased, the yield of the photoproduct decreased. All these triplet energies are sufficient for the formation of singlet molecular oxygen ¹O₂ (¹Δ_g) (energy is 22.5 kcal mol⁻¹) but rose bengal, eosin and fluorescein have enough triplet energy for the transfer to form the singlet molecular oxygen ¹O₂ (¹Σ_g⁺) (energy is 37.35 kcal mol⁻¹). The energy difference in triplet states of the dye and the triplet state of molecular oxygen is in the order : fluorescein > eosin > rose bengal > methylene blue.

As the difference in these two states increases, there is less probability of formation of singlet oxygen (¹Δ_g), which is responsible for the oxidation and as a consequence, the yield decreases. The life time of sigma oxygen (¹Σ_g⁺) is 10⁻⁹ s in liquid phase whereas that of delta oxygen (¹Δ_g) is 10⁻³ s. So sigma singlet oxygen (¹Σ_g⁺) is readily quenched in solution and therefore, ¹O₂ (¹Δ_g) may be considered as responsible for the oxidation.

Effect of nature of solvent :

The effect of the nature of the solvent on photooxidation of thiopentone and phenytoin was investigated using

different solvents. Yield of the product in different solvents have been determined. Results are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of nature of solvent

[Sensitizer] = 1.0×10^{-5} M, irradiation time = 13 h, irradiation time = 49 h

Sensitizer	Life time of singlet oxygen (μ s)	Yield (%)	
		Thiopentone	Phenytoin
Water	2.0	21.9	10.2
Methanol	8.5	20.7	9.8
Ethanol	12.0	21.2	9.8
<i>n</i> -Butanol	18.2	20.3	9.5

It was observed that the yield was higher in non-polar or partially polar solvents. The yield was found to increase as the polarity of the solvent decreases. This may be attributed to the longer life time of singlet oxygen in partially polar or non-polar solvents, which will provide the singlet molecular oxygen enough time to react with the substrate (drug).

Effect of the singlet oxygen scavengers :

The effect of singlet oxygen scavenger on the percentage yield of the dye sensitized photooxidation of thiopentone and phenytoin was also determined to ascertain the participation of singlet oxygen in the reaction. The results are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of the singlet oxygen scavengers

[Sensitizer] = 1.0×10^{-5} M, irradiation time = 12 h, irradiation time = 22 h

Sensitizer	Yield (%)	
	Thiopentone	Phenytoin
-	21.9	10.2
DABCO	4.9	0.5
Cobalt chloride	5.0	0.8
α -Tocopherol	5.3	0.8

It was observed that there is rapid fall in the yield of the product from 21.9% (in absence of scavenger) to 4.9% and 10.2% (in absence of scavenger) to 0.5% of thiopentone and phenytoin, respectively, in the presence of scavenger. This confirms the participation of singlet molecular oxygen as an active oxidizing species in the reaction.

Results and discussion

The photooxidation product of thiopentone and phenytoin was characterized by physical, chemical and spectral data.

The photo-oxygenated product (1a) of thiopentone was obtained as golden colored crystal and the molecular formula was determined as $C_{22}H_{38}N_4S_2O_2$ by elemental analysis as shown in the Table 4.

The IR spectrum of the product showed various bands as shown in Table 5.

Table 4. Elemental analysis of product (1a)

Elemental	Calcd. (%)	Found (%)
C	58.15	58.31
H	8.37	8.33
N	12.33	12.38
O	7.85	7.15
S	14.10	14.15

Table 5. IR spectrum of product (1a)

Bands (cm^{-1})	Type of vibration	Group
503	S-S str.	-S-S-
686	C-S str.	-C-S-
1427	C-N str.	Substituted cyclic amide
1610	N-H bend.	Imine
1673	C=O str.	Ketone
2960	C-H str.	Methyl

From the above data, the product was characterized as :

The above structure has also been confirmed by usual chemical test for -S-S- linkage.

The photo-oxygenated product (1b) of phenytoin was obtained as brown crystal and the molecular formula was determined as $C_{30}H_{22}N_4O_4$ by elemental analysis as shown in the Table 6.

The IR spectrum of the product showed various bands as shown in Table 7.

Table 6. Elemental analysis of product (1a)

Elemental	Calcd. (%)	Found (%)
C	71.71	71.48
H	4.38	4.39
N	11.16	11.19
O	12.75	12.70

Table 7. IR spectrum of product (1b)

Bands (cm ⁻¹)	Type of vibration	Group
1465, 1490	C=C str.	Aromatic
1605	C=C str.	Aromatic
1470	N-N str.	-
1742	C=O str.	Ketone
3000	C-H str.	Aromatic

From the above data, the product was characterized as :

The above structure has also been confirmed by usual chemical test for -N-N- linkage.

Mechanism :

From above data, a tentative mechanism for this reaction has been proposed as shown in Diagram 1. The first step of the reaction is the excitation of the dye molecule to its first excited singlet state, which undergoes intersystem crossing (ISC) to give its corresponding triplet state. The triplet reacts further with ground state of oxygen (³O₂) to generate singlet oxygen (¹O₂) to generate singlet oxygen. In the second (a) step, singlet molecular oxygen abstracts an electron from thiopentone ion to form a -S[•] radical. This radical then dimerises to give the final product having -S-S- linkage. Such a dimerization is supported by the observations made

Step I : Generation of singlet molecular oxygen

[D : Dye (a sensitizer)]

Step II(a) : Reaction of singlet oxygen with thiopentone

Step II(b) : Reaction of singlet oxygen with phenytoin

Diagram 1

by earlier workers¹⁸. In the second (b) case, singlet molecular oxygen abstracts a proton from imine group in phenytoin to generate a radical. This radical then dimerises to give the final product.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. V. K. Sharma and Dr. P. B. Punjabi for critical discussion.

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